

Supplementary material

Potentials and hotspots of post-lithium-ion batteries: environmental impacts and supply risks for sodium- and potassium-ion batteries

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1. Production process of the target batteries

Fig. S1 Production process for Na_{1.1}(Ni_{0.3}Mn_{0.5}Mg_{0.05}Ti_{0.05})O₂-Hard carbon SIB (NMMT).

Fig. S2 Production process for $\text{Na}_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ - $\text{Na}_3\text{LiTi}_5\text{O}_{12}$ SIB (NTO).

Fig. S3 Production process for KFeSO_4F -Graphite PIB (KFSF).

Fig. S4 Production process for $\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ -Graphite LIB (NMC).

Fig. S5 Production process for LiFePO_4 -Graphite LIB (LFP).

Fig. S6 Production process for LiFePO₄-Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ LIB (LTO).

Fig. S7 Weight composition of the battery cells.

2. Additional results for environmental impacts

Weighting results for the three endpoints of environmental aspects showed that the impacts on human health were dominant (**Fig. S8**). Although the results for the three endpoints exhibited similar trends with the overall results for environmental impacts (**Fig. S8**), some midpoint-level results showed different trends (**Figs. S9–S12**).

Regarding human health, global warming (GW), particulate matter (PM), and human toxicity (HT) were the main contributors (**Fig. S9**). LTO displayed the largest impacts for most midpoints for human health, except for water use (WU). NMC showed the largest impacts for WU, mainly attributed to the production of nickel sulfate (NiSO_4) and cobalt sulfate (CoSO_4) for the cathode. NTO had the second largest impacts for some midpoints, due to the production of titanium dioxide (TiO_2) for the anode, as well as the BMS and electricity. Environmental impacts associated with KFSF were relatively small except for Stratospheric ozone depletion (SO). KFSF showed a relatively large impact on SO, owing to the production of nitric acid for the anode.

Global warming (GW) and Terrestrial acidification (TA) were the main contributors to ecosystems (**Fig. S10**). Similar to the results for human health, LTO showed the largest impacts for most midpoints for ecosystems. NMC showed the largest impacts for water use (WU), mainly attributed to the production of NiSO_4 and CoSO_4 for the cathode. BMS and electricity were the main contributors to NTO because its energy density was relatively low. In addition, the anode was also the main contributor to NTO for some midpoints, mainly attributed to the production of TiO_2 . The anode contributed to some midpoints for KFSF because of the electricity generated in China for graphite production.

Regarding resources, fossil resources (FR) was the main contributor (**Fig. S11**). LTO showed the largest impacts for mineral resources (MR) and FR, both of which were mainly attributed to the production of TiO_2 and lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3) for the anode and lithium hydroxide (LiOH) for the cathode. NMC had the second largest impact for MR, mainly due to the production of NiSO_4 . NTO showed the second largest impact on FR, mainly due to heat and TiO_2 production. The impact for MR associated with KFSF was the smallest. KFSF had a larger impact for FR than NMC, mainly because of its lower energy density.

The results demonstrated that some midpoints had different results from weighting results (i.e., total environmental impact). For example, NMC had the best performance for global warming, which is a main impact category and frequently discussed in LCA studies. However, it did not show the best performances for some impact categories such as particulate matter and human toxicity, resulting in the third largest environmental impacts for NMC (**Figs. S8 and S12**). These suggest that only midpoint-level discussion may result in misleading conclusions. Meanwhile, it should be noted that weighting involves uncertainty and thus discussion based on both midpoint- and endpoint-level results is desirable.

Fig. S8 Weighting results for environmental impacts and environmental damages of the three endpoints for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

Fig. S9 Environmental impacts on human health in different impact categories for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

Fig. S10 Environmental impacts on ecosystems in different impact categories for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

Fig. S11 Environmental impacts on resources in different impact categories for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

Fig. S12 Environmental impacts in different impact categories at midpoints for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

3. Additional results for supply risks

Fig. S13 Results for midpoints of the supply risks for the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries.

3. Additional results for discussion

Fig. S14 Comparison of environmental impacts associated with the production of 1 kWh of the six batteries calculated using ecoinvent and GaBi database (excluding BMS). EI: ecoinvent.

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